

A NOTE ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF TETRAIODOACETONE

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It has been pointed out in a previous communication (MacMahon and Srivastava, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 311) that the reaction between sodium citrate and iodine (dissolved in KI) is negligibly slow both in light and dark at room temperature, but in the presence of certain catalysts such as Mn^{++} and Fe^{+++} the reaction proceeds rapidly in light with the production of a solid product. This solid compound has now been prepared in sufficient quantities by the following method.

Concentrated solution of sodium citrate was mixed with iodine solution in presence of small quantities of Mn^{++} and exposed to sunlight till the iodine was used up. The solid product formed was filtered off and the clear filtrate again exposed to sunlight after the addition of more iodine solution. The above operation was repeated until no further reaction with iodine took place. The yellow solid product, thus obtained, when recrystallised from warm benzene in the dark, melted at 142° with a previous change in colour. The molecular weight as determined by the cryoscopic method in the dark using benzene as solvent, and its percentage of iodine content, both correspond to the formula of tetraiodoacetone (CHI_2COCHI_2). This appears to be a convenient method for the preparation of the above compound and might be used as an alternative to the methods found in literature. [Lederer, *Fortschritte der Theerfarbenfabrikation*, 5, 710; Angeli and Levi, *Gazzetta*, 1893, 23, 97].

At 22° the solubility of the compound in benzene is found to 3.4 g. per 100 g. of solvent. It is also soluble in toluene and to a lesser extent in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and acetic acid. These solutions are extremely sensitive and decompose photochemically producing free iodine and a solid resinous compound. In dark the solutions are fairly stable at room temperature (about 20°) but by raising the temperature to 40° decomposition takes place slowly.

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